

THE EFFECTS OF SOCIAL MEDIA ADDICTION AMONG STUDENTS IN THE TERTIARY INSTITUTION: A CASE STUDY OF THE DEPARTMENT OF COMPUTER SCIENCE, KOGI STATE UNIVERSITY, ANYIGBA, KOGI STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

Platforms for social interaction and unrestricted information exchange have been made possible by the social media network's emergency. Finding out whether social media addiction affects students' academic performance at Kogi State University, Anyigba, Kogi State, is the main goal of this study. To gather information from the respondents, an online survey form was employed as a questionnaire. It was shown that there was a correlation between the amount of time spent on social media and academic study. In conclusion, it has been deduced from the analysis and hypothesis that, with the exception of severe addiction, student use of social media does not generally result in poor academic performance.

Keywords: social media, social networking, addiction, networking, academic, blogs, education.

I. Introduction

The advent of internet which to humanity has liberated a lot of stresses or cost in terms of exchanging of information from one place to another, availability of quality textbooks for research in the library is being misusing. The Internet is a global networking system that can be used on most devices nowadays and has become an essential part of our lives. In today's technological era, most of the companies are getting their operations done over the Internet. There are various uses of the Internet by which companies and individuals are making their daily tasks more productive and more comfortable. Among the few major uses of internet are research, online banking and trading, education, social networking, E-commerce, and

advertising. Social media are websites and applications that enable users to create and share content or to participate in social networking. The growth and popularity of social media has created a new world of collaboration and communication. Social media is an online interaction site where people interact to build, share and change their idea and comments regarding any information [1]. Social media is generally used as an umbrella term that describes a variety of online platforms, including blogs, business networks, collaborative projects, enterprise social networks (SN), forums, microblogs, photo sharing, products review, social bookmarking, social gaming, SN, video sharing, and virtual worlds [2], [3] and [4].

Social media penetration in Nigeria and the negative consequences are on the rise. One of the consequences is social media addiction. On the internet, people engage in a variety of activities some of which may be potentially to be addictive. The mass appeal of social networks on the internet could potentially be a cause for concern, particularly when attending to the gradually increasing amounts of time people spend online [5], [6]. Social media addiction is a behavioural addiction that is characterized as being overly concerned about social media, driven by an uncontrollable urge to log on to or use social media, and devoting so much time and effort to social media that it impairs other important life areas. The addiction of social media is affecting students in their respective academic performances.

II. Review of Related Works

Social Networking Sites (SNSs) are virtual communities where users can construct individual public profiles, interact with real-life friends, and meet other people based on shared benefits. They are seen as a 'global consumer wonder' with an exponential or geometrical rise in usage within the last few years [5]. According to [7], social media addiction is prevalent among young people. Several approaches had been widely used among young people but it's superficial. In recent years, with the expansion of information technology, especially with the rapid propagation of internet-based social media (e.g., Facebook, WeChat, Twitter or Instagram), the ways of interpersonal communication have drastically changed [8]. The global social media platforms and the easy access to the internet bring about the potential for social media addiction, namely, the irrational and excessive use of social media to the extent that it interferes with other aspects of daily life. The massive growth of social media has led to the global concern of social media addiction, which affects a large portion of society. Addicts of social media can be identified using a variety of parameters including conflict, mood swings, behavioural changes and conflict. With the increasing use of social media, the addictive use of this new technology also grows. Previous studies found that addictive social media use is associated with negative consequences such as reduced productivity, unhealthy social relationships, and reduced life-satisfaction [9]. However, in the paper by [10], the

addiction symptoms linked with SNS addiction were cognitive and behavioural salience, conflict with other activities, euphoria, loss of control, withdrawal, and relapse/reinstatement.

Those with low self-worth are most probable to fall into social network addiction due to unsound social exposure with people. As such, there is an urgent need for further research in terms of behavioural addiction. As social media has become an essential platform for online communication, a number of research have investigated on its behavioural effects on excessive usage [11]. Meanwhile, another problem of social media is depression as indicated by [12] and also can cause mental problems to some users [5]. In another view, social media addiction like any other type of addiction is also governed by personal lifestyle and health habits. This type of addiction has been classified as a type of behavioural addiction which stems mostly from problems in personal and social life [13].

In another dimension, as narrated by [14] and [15], that a behaviour can be defined as addiction if it has these six components, such as salience, mood modification, tolerance, withdrawal symptoms, conflicts, and relapse. And other summarized three overarching theoretical perspectives include cognitive-behavioural model, social skill model and socio-cognitive model accordingly.

The addiction of social media is affecting students in their respective academic performances. As such, student's academic performance is affected by a large number of factors but the impact of social media on the performance of student is most important than any other factor. In the research paper presented by [16] and [17], stated that people consume additional time in interacting with their friends to access and or share information on social media platforms. So, they become addicted to always look over and verify their status after every few minutes in a day. Current statistics show that university students in Nigeria are under increased pressure due to higher academic standards in other countries, and it has become more important than ever for educators to encourage graduation and further education [18].

III. Objectives

The broader aim of this study is to examine the effects of social media on the students' academic performance. The other specific objectives of the study are as follow:

1. To ascertain how the use of social media do influence the academic performance of the students.
2. To find out whether the number of hours used on social media platform has any positive or negative influence on their academic performance.
3. To determine whether social media usage/addiction depends on the sex of the students.

IV. Research Questions

The following are the research questions raised for the study.

1. Does the number of hour (s) use on social media have influence on the academic performance of the students?
2. To what level would student addictiveness to social network influence their academic performance?
3. Does the social media network that the students are more exposed to have impact on their academic performance?
4. Is there gender variance in the student’s usage of social media network?

V. Material and Methods

This study investigates the effects of social media on students’ academic performance of undergraduate and postgraduate in the Department of Computer Science, Kogi State University, Anyigba, Kogi State. The methodology adopted for this study are quantitative and descriptive research approaches. Surveys play a main role in the research methodology. Survey-maker was used to administer online questionnaire to students. The questionnaires used in the survey are closed-ended that can be easily analysed by qualitative data. The population is this study comprises of all 257 students both the undergraduates and postgraduate in the department of Computer Science, Faculty of Natural Sciences, Kogi State University, Anyigba, Kogi State, Nigeria. The instrument for data collection was online Google form to the students in the department. Out of 257 students (respondents), only 250 responded to the questionnaires. The results are presented in in frequency distribution, charts and in the tabular form. The statistical analysis used is the Chi-square (χ^2) to determine whether relationship exist between the statements in contention.

VI. Results Presentation

Table 1: Demographic Information of the Respondents

Item	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Sex		
Male	208	83%
Female	42	17%
Total	250	100%
Level		
100	68	27%
200	64	26%

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300	68	27%
400	50	20%
Total	250	100%
Age Group		
18-20	92	37%
21-23	74	30%
24-25	84	33%
Total	250	100%

Fig. 6.1: Demographic Information of Respondents.

Fig. 6.2: Number of Students at Undergraduate Level.

Fig. 6.3: Age Group for Undergraduate Students.

Table 2: Responses of Social Media Apps used by the Students

Social Media Apps	No of Users	Percentage (%)
Facebook	240	25%
WhatsApp	228	24%
Twitter	160	17%
Instagram	122	13%
Telegram	80	9%
LinkedIn	54	6%
Skype	32	4%
Other	22	2%
Total	958	100%

Fig. 6.4: Social Media Apps used by the Students.

Research Question 1: Does the number of hour (s) use on social media have influence on the academic performance of the students?

Table 3: Number of Hours used by the Respondents on Social Media

S/N	No of Minutes/Hours used Per Day	SA	A	D	SD	Total
1	At most 30 minutes	35	25	80	110	250
2	At most 1 hour	30	55	65	100	250
3	At most 2 hours	71	52	70	57	250
4	At most 3 hours	85	50	65	50	250
5	At most 4 hours	53	42	55	100	250
6	More than 4 hours	12	22	96	120	250
	Total	286	246	431	537	1500

Research Question 2: To what level would student addictiveness to social network influence their academic performance?

Table 4: Students Addictiveness to Social Network and Academic Performance

S/N	Statement	SA	A	D	SD	Total
1	Addiction to social media is a problematic issue that affects my academic life.	107 (43%)	85 (34%)	43 (17%)	15 (6%)	250 (100%)
2	Online social networks distract me from my studies.	120 (48%)	82 (33%)	40 (16%)	8 (3%)	250 (100%)
3	Hours spent on social media is more than the number of hours spent studying.	128 (51%)	80 (32%)	37 (15%)	5 (2%)	250 (100%)
4	There is no improvement in my grade since I involved in social media networking.	42 (17%)	30 (12%)	100 (40%)	78 (31%)	250 (100%)
	Total Percentage (%)	397 (40%)	277 (28%)	220 (21%)	106 (11%)	1000 (100%)

Research Question 3: Does the social media network that the students are more exposed to impact their academic performance?

Table 5: Exposure of Students to Social Media Network and Their Academic Performance

S/N	Statement	SA	A	D	SD	Total
1	I make use of WhatsApp to circulate knowledge/information to my classmate.	72 (29%)	105 (42%)	58 (23%)	15 (6%)	250 (100%)
2	I usually participate in academic conversation on Twitter this has improve my academic performance.	98 (39%)	52 (21%)	68 (27%)	32 (13%)	250 (100%)
3	I always have unrestricted access to Facebook and this has affected my performance destructively.	54 (22%)	95 (38%)	70 (28%)	31 (12%)	250 (100%)
4	I do not rely on information gotten from social media platform for my academic work.	130 (52%)	65 (26%)	40 (16%)	15 (6%)	250 (100%)
Total Percentage (%)		354 (35%)	317 (32%)	236 (24%)	93 (9%)	1000 (100%)

Research Question 4: Is there gender variance in the student's usage of social media network?

Table 6: Gender Usage of Social Media Network

S/N	Statement	SA	A	D	SD	Total
1	Gender determines the level of social media network usage.	45 (18%)	124 (50%)	25 (10%)	56 (22%)	250 (100%)
2	Males are active at using social network sites for non-academic purpose.	134 (54%)	66 (26%)	30 (12%)	20 (8%)	250 (100%)
3	Female students use social networking sites more to clearly nurture social connections.	151 (60%)	53 (21%)	10 (4%)	36 (15%)	250 (100%)

4.	Male and female students use social networks differently in diverse frequencies.	58 (23%)	138 (55%)	19 (8%)	35 (14%)	250 (100%)
Total Percentage (%)		388 (39%)	381 (38%)	84 (8%)	147 (15%)	1000 (100%)

VII. Data Analysis and Testing of Hypotheses

In testing the hypotheses stated, we used chi-square (χ^2) inferential statistics to show whether relationships exist between them and to determine the level of significance. The significant level used in this research is 0.05, and that indicates a 5% risk of concluding that a relationship exists when there is no actual relationship.

Hypothesis 1:

H_0 : The number of hour (s) use on social media have influence on the academic performance of the students.

H_1 : The number of hour (s) use on social media have no influence on the academic performance of the students.

Table 7: Chi-square Analysis of How the Number of Hours Spent on Social Media have Influence on the Academic Performance of Students

Variable	N	Df	α	χ^2 tabulated	χ^2 calculated	Decision
Number of hours spent on social media networks have influence on academic performance of students.	250	15	0.05	24.99	164.00	Rejected

Hypothesis 2:

H_0 : Students addictiveness to social media networks have negative influence on their academic performance.

H_1 : Students addictiveness to social media networks does not negative influence on their academic performance.

Table 8: Chi-square Analysis of Students Addictiveness to Social Network and Influence on their Academic Performance

Variable	N	Df	α	χ^2 tabulated	χ^2 calculated	Decision
Students' addictiveness to social networks and influence on their academic performance.	250	9	0.05	16.92	260.99	Rejected

Hypothesis 3: The social media network that the students are more exposed to have impact on their academic performance.

H₀: Social media networks that the students are more exposed to have positive impact on their academic performance.

H₁: Social media networks that the students are more exposed to have negative impact on their academic performance.

Table 9: Chi-square Analysis on Exposure of Students to Social Media Network and their Academic Performance

Variable	N	Df	α	χ^2 tabulated	χ^2 calculated	Decision
Exposure of students to social media networks and their academic performance.	250	9	0.05	16.92	81.73	Rejected

Hypothesis 4: The gender variance in the students' usage of social media network.

H₀: There is a significant difference in the usage of social media networks by both male and female students.

H₁: There is no significant difference between male and female students in the usage of social media networks.

Table 10: Chi-square Analysis of Gender Usage of Social Media Networks

Variable	N	Df	α	χ^2 tabulated	χ^2 calculated	Decision
The gender variance in the students' usage of social media networks.	250	9	0.05	16.92	171.71	Rejected

VIII. Conclusion

According to this study, social media addiction is a problem that primarily affects adults and students. It is a growing source of concern and demands prompt attention. Addiction of any kind must be controlled since it harms society. It is crucial that we inform everyone around us about the circumstance and the negative impacts it may have on our relationships with friends, family, and co-workers.

Addiction to social media also prevents a person from growing and developing personally. Therefore, while it is beneficial to connect and share with others using social media, it is also crucial that we do not neglect our in-person contacts.

For both young people and people all over the world, social media has evolved into a crucial instrument for interpersonal contact. Young people need guidance from parents, instructors, and counsellors in order to use social media responsibly and avoid developing a social media addiction. Counsellors must be extremely knowledgeable about the mental health of and the issues that may affect young people who are hooked to social media in order to provide better counselling services.

Counsellors must also be familiar with the traits of social media addiction and practice more treatments for young people that have been proven effective in study.

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